

BUCKLING AND POST-BUCKLING BEHAVIOUR OF TOP-HAT CROSS-SECTION COMPOSITE BEAMS WITH VARIOUS SEQUENCES OF PLYS

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1 Introduction

Polymeric composites – the laminates - are currently one of the most developing materials group applied in contemporary thin-walled structures. This yields from an advantageous set of physical-chemical and mechanical properties, particularly high strength in relation to low mass density of the composite material [1, 2]. From a wide group of laminates mainly those having epoxy matrix reinforced with glass, carbon or kevlar fibers find applications. Exceptionally advantageous strength characteristics of a laminate can be obtained by utilization of advanced forming techniques of polymeric composites, such as autoclaving [3].

In design process of complex composite materials an important role plays a sequence of plies, having a decisive influence on load carrying abilities of particular components of the stress state. This applies to thin-walled composite structures stability as well, in which a specific ply sequence can have essential influence on a value of critical load or a structure's stiffness in post-critical state [4].

In this work, results of experimental tests on thin-walled composite columns of top-hat cross-section subjected to compressive load were presented. The obtained research results allow to verify the results given by FE models, as well as by author's own analytical-numerical (ANM) method based on the Koiter theory [5]. The experiments covered also determination of material properties, used later in worked out numerical models. Such approach allowed more credible comparison of the prepared composite profiles behaviour with numerical models, being usually only models of ideal structures.

2 Object of research

The object of the research was the thin-walled beam made of carbon-epoxy composite formed into a top-hat cross-section with the following dimensions: 80x40x1.048 mm (the cross-section) and L=300 mm (the length) – Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Dimension of the analyzed columns

The composite had epoxy matrix having the following characteristics: mass density: 1.24 g/cm³; curing temperature: 128 °C; tensile strength: 64 MPa; Poisson ratio: 0.4; Young modulus in tension: 5.1 GPa. For reinforcement the AS7J12K carbon fibres were used with mass density: 2.5 g/cm³; tensile strength: 4830 MPa; Poisson ratio: 0.269; Young modulus in tension: 241 GPa. Nominal volume fraction of the reinforcement was approximately equals 60%.

For the used composite pre-pregs the following mechanical characteristics were determined experimentally according to the ISO standard: Young moduli: $E_1 = 130.71$ GPa, $E_2 = 6.36$ GPa, Kirchhoff modulus: $G_{12} = 4.18$ GPa, Poisson ratio:

$\nu_{12} = 0.32$. The experimentally determined strength characteristics of the carbon-epoxy composite were exploited in the definition of material model in the FEM calculations.

Two types of 8-ply composite columns were tested. The layups were symmetrical, as follows: (a) - $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ and (b) - $[45/-45/90/0]_s$. Each ply had the same thickness of 0.131 mm. In Fig. 2 the used ply sequence was given.

Fig. 2. Layup arrangement used in the research: a) $[90/45/-45/0]_s$, b) $[45/-45/90/0]_s$

3 Production and quality control of the composite columns

The composites were produced with autoclaving technique in the Department of Material Engineering at the Lublin University of Technology [1,6-8]. The production process comprised preparation of a hermetic vacuum packet in a special air-conditioned clean room on a dedicated mould allowing to map the shape and dimensions of the produced profiles - Fig. 3.

Fig.3. Production of composite columns: a) hermetic vacuum packet, b) the autoclave

The prepared hermetic packet, providing stable sub-atmospheric pressure of ca -0.1 MPa was subjected to polymerization process in a laboratory-autoclave, where an overpressure of 0.4 MPa was kept in order to provide required holding down. In case of the carbon-epoxy composite a temperature of material heating of 135 °C was kept for 2 hours, what enabled finishing of the prepreg polymerization process. In order to eliminate disadvantageous phenomena usually emerging during the composite production process (excessive increase of thermal stresses inside the material and restraining of proper relaxation of initial and thermal stresses) a precise heating and cooling rate of 0.033 K/s was applied.

The manufactured composite columns underwent texture quality control of the laminate with non-destructive testing (NDT) methods and microstructural inspection considering a localization of possible flaw. The flaw can have a form of delamination or porosity cluster. They are the most frequently occurring laminate defects and can seriously deteriorate the material strength. Moreover, they can be sources of failure of the composite structure. The NDT tests were done with OmniScan MXU-M ultrasonic defectoscope, equipped with Olympus 5L64 A12 measurement head. The walls of all the produced profiles were inspected considering flaw identification. The A-scan and the B-scan techniques were used, as they allowed to localize and to dimension the possible flaw within the material [9,10] – Fig.4.

Fig. 4. NDT quality control of the laminates

Additionally, microstructural research was lead with X-ray micro-tomography (SkyScan 1174 microtomograph) and with optical microscopy (Nikon MA200). Both techniques employed

computer-assisted image analysis (Image Pro Plus, NIS-Elements). These methods enabled additional analysis of the composite profiles round corners' radii, where a possibility of discontinuity in the form of interlayer delamination was particularly high. The performed measurement confirmed very good quality of the manufactured composite profiles, as no internal flaws were detected – Fig.5.

Fig. 5. Optical image of composite microstructure

4 Experimental investigation

The experimental tests were conducted on axially compressed thin-walled composite columns with top-hat cross-section. Stand tests were done with the Zwick Z100/SN3A 1-accuracy class universal testing machine of the 100 kN load range – Fig.6. Any imperfections of the columns' ends, able to cause unwanted boundary effects, were compensated by specially prepared soft-plastic pads. Before each test the loading system was loaded up to 15 % of the expected critical load in order to provide best alignment of the column placed between the grips. Next, the grip retainers were removed and the column was completely unloaded. On the specimen's internal and external surfaces in the vicinity of the biggest web's deflection area Vishay's electrical strain gauges were stuck along the loading direction. The two CEA-06-125UW-350 series gauges had a constant $k=2.135\pm 0.5\%$ and electrical resistance of $350\ \Omega\pm 0.3\%$. In addition the deflections were measured with the optoNCDT 1605 laser dilatometer. All the measurement elements were plugged to the MGCplus system (Hottinger). During the tests the indications of all sensors were registered with a frequency of 1 Hz.

Fig. 6. The test stand with a composite sample

All tests were conducted in standard conditions, at 23 °C with constant velocity of the cross-bar equal to 2 mm/min. The experiments were lead in sub-critical range with registration of parameters needed in determination of critical loads, as well as in post-critical range. For each of the considered ply sequences three samples were tested and the measurements were done thrice. Thus, nine measurements were performed for each layup in order to determine the columns' sub- and post-critical characteristics.

5 Experimental methods for buckling loads determination

On the basis of the obtained experimental results the values of critical load were determined, in accordance with the following methods:

- a) the vertical-tangent line method (the mean-strains method) – denoted as K1 [11,12,13],
- b) the method of straight lines intersection in the plot of mean strains – denoted as K2 [11,12,13],
- c) the P-w² method – denoted as K3 [11,12,13],
- d) the inflexion-point method – denoted as K4 [12],
- e) the Tereszowski method – denoted as K5 [14],
- f) the Koiter method – denoted as K6 [5,15].

The methods for the critical load determination employed in the conducted research demand approximative calculations based on results of experimental measurements. The computations performed in such a way had in target matching the functions describing the analyzed phenomena with the experimental outcomes. Note, that an appropriate

choice of measurement points from all the accessible data was crucial and decisive for the final results of calculations. It was connected to an idea of the so-called *pivotal points* elaborated by Bronshtein and Semendyayev [16] and implemented by Spencer and Walker [17] in an analysis of experimental results for plates. This idea states, that appropriate choice of the *pivotal points* leads to sufficiently optimal matching of the analyzed function to experimental data.

Exemplary results of deflection w and strains ε measurements for the $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ -sequence column are presented in Figs 7-9. The elaborated relations between the displacements or the strains and the external load enabled the determination of the critical load with the methods K1 - K3, whereas the values of the critical load determined with the methods K4 - K6 were obtained numerically.

Fig. 7. Dependence of compression load on deformations ε_1 , ε_2 and $\varepsilon_m = 0,5(\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2)$ - the mean-strains method (K1)

Fig. 8. Dependence of compression load on deformations $\varepsilon_m = 0,5(\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2)$ - the method of straight lines intersection in the plot of mean strains (K2)

Fig. 9. Dependence of compression load on square dimensionless deflection $w^2 = (w/w_{\max})^2$ (K3)

6 Numerical calculations

The finite element method and analytical-numerical method were employed to buckling analysis and post buckling behaviour of thin-walled composite columns. Two different software packages (ABAQUS® and ANSYS®) were used for numerical calculation. They were thin-walled plane-stress shell elements with 8 nodes (S8R - in ABAQUS® and SHELL 99 - in ANSYS®). Both used elements have six degree of freedom at each node. A *Layup-Ply* technique was employed for the purpose of the symmetrical laminate modelling. A numerical model of the top-hat section composite columns is presented in Fig.10.

Fig. 10. FEM model of composite column

Boundary conditions of the numerical model representing articulated support of the column's ends were defined by restraining the kinematic degrees of freedom of the nodes belonging to the borders of the first and the last cross-section. The load was applied to the model as uniformly distributed concentrated forces at the top-end of the column (Fig.10).

The properties of composite material were described by definition of orthotropic material in plane stress state, what allowed to describe the laminate properties in particular directions, according to fibres' arrangement. The numerical calculations within the framework of FE were performed in two stages. The linear stability problem (critical state) was solved by finding critical load and buckling mode, as well. Verification of the obtained results was performed with the ANM method [18], based on the Koiter's general asymptotic theory of conservative systems stability [5]. In Figs 11 and 12 the lowest buckling modes of the analyzed columns obtained numerically were presented in comparison with experimental outcomes. The obtained buckling modes exhibited different numbers of the half-waves along the column's symmetry axis, depending on the layup – the $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ -sequence column had 7 halfwaves, whereas the $[45/-45/90/0]_s$ one – 5 halfwaves. The critical load values determined with the methods K1 - K6 using the experimental results were compared with the numerical, as well as the analytical-numerical results – see Figs 13 and 14.

Fig. 11. Buckling mode of the $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ - sequence column

Fig. 12. Buckling mode of the $[45/-45/90/0]_s$ - sequence column

Fig. 13. Critical load values for the $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ -sequence column

Fig. 14. Critical load values for the $[45/-45/90/0]_s$ - sequence column

The post-critical calculations were performed as non-linear static analysis of the structure with initiated imperfections having a dimension of 0.1 of the top-hat profile wall thickness, corresponding to

the first instability mode of the column. The post-critical analysis taking into account geometrically non-linear problem in Abaqus was done with incremental-iterative Newton-Raphson method, whereas the post-critical equilibrium path was tracked with the Arc-length procedure (the Ricks Method) in the Ansys program. The range of the numerical calculations covered also an attempt to estimate a probability of the composite damage occurrence in post-critical state according to the Tsai-Wu criterion [19-22].

The postcritical *force-deflection* ($P-w$) equilibrium paths calculated numerically up to ca. 150 % of the critical load were compared with experimental results – Figs 15 and 16.

Fig.15. Comparison of post-buckling paths obtained numerically with experimental results for the $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ -sequence column

Fig.16. Comparison of post-buckling paths obtained numerically with experimental results for the $[45/-45/90/0]_s$ -sequence column

Post-critical range analysis enabled to assess the deformation and the stiffness of the structure after the stability loss in relation to the laminate's ply sequence. The experimental tests were lead within the range exceeding ca. 1.5-times the critical forces values obtained numerically with the FEM. An attempt was made to assess the failure load value in accordance with the Tsai-Wu criterion [19,20]. In Fig. 17 the post-critical deformation of the compressed columns corresponding to the failure load value was presented (the Tsai-Wu-criterion failure parameter equal to 1).

Fig. 17. Post-critical deformation state (Tsai-Wu criterion): a) $[90/45/-45/0]_s$, b) slup $[45/-45/90/0]_s$

7 Comparison of the results

The analysis of the critical state outcomes for the compressed composite columns shows a complete qualitative agreement of the buckling modes obtained with each of the exploited methods (FEM, ANM and the experiments). In each case the same number of half-waves along the column's axis direction was obtained, what characterized the structure's buckling mode for the lowest value of the critical load. High conformity of the results was observed also for the value of the critical load determined numerically (with the Abaqus, the Ansys and the ANM) with the experimental results obtained with the methods K1 - K6 (Figs 13 and 14). The quantitative analysis of the critical load values exhibited maximal discrepancies of the obtained results for the methods ANM and K2: 13.9 % for the column with the $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ ply sequence and 10.7 % for the $[45/-45/90/0]_s$ one. Rejection of the extreme values determined experimentally allowed

to decrease the discrepancy below 10 %, what in case of the structure stability research meant high compatibility of the results. The discrepancy of the numerical results did not overcome 5 %.

The obtained results allowed to assess the influence of the sequence of plies on the value of the critical load. It was observed, that moving the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies outside the sequence (cf. the $[45/-45/90/0]_s$ -sequence column) lead to an increase of the critical load in comparison to the $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ sequence by ca. 25 %.

Post-critical equilibrium paths were also determined for the nodes experiencing maximal amplitudes of displacement in a slightly post-critical state. Figs. 15 and 16 present the results of experiments, as well as the FEM and the ANM method results in dimensional coordinate system ($P-w$). The presented characteristics exhibit high conformity of the obtained results for all the exploited research methods. Maximal quantitative differences were obtained for the $[90/45/-45/0]_s$ -sequence column at a level of 18 % and in case of the $[45/-45/90/0]_s$ -sequence column – 14 % (ANM/Abaqus).

The analysis of the post-critical equilibrium path allows to assess the structure's stiffness after the loss of stability in the context of applied ply sequence. In both cases within the postcritical range up to 150 % of the critical load similar stiffness of the tested structures was observed, what was reflected by close inclination angles of both characteristics. Comparison of the postcritical equilibrium paths in function of the composite's ply sequence for the FEM and the ANM calculations, as well as the experimental outcomes is presented in Figs 18 - 20.

Fig. 18. Comparison of postcritical equilibrium paths – FEM results

Fig. 19. Comparison of postcritical equilibrium paths – ANM results

Fig. 20. Comparison of postcritical equilibrium paths – experimental results

8 Conclusions

The paper presents studies on critical, as well as post-critical state of thin-walled composite columns subjected to axial compression. The performed analysis proved qualitative and quantitative agreement of the research results made with different methods. Analysis of the curves shown in Fig. 15 and 16 reveals good agreement of computational results with those of experiments, both in subcritical and post-critical range. This confirms the adequacy of the worked out numerical models. The postcritical equilibrium paths determined with the analytical-numerical method (ANM) exhibit slightly lesser stiffness in comparison with the numerical (FEM) results. Moreover, one can spot, that the experimental results shown in Figs 15 and 16 are located between postcritical equilibrium paths determined with the ANM and the FEM methods. It allows to verify

advantageously calculations' results in relation to the characteristics of the real structures.

Comparison of the results within a context of the applied ply sequence exhibits a considerable increase of the critical load's value through location of the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies outside, having kept the geometrical and material parameters of the structure. Thus, the obtained results delivered a lot of important information useful in the process of forming and optimization of the composite texture in the context of its maintenance loading conditions [23].

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